

Human-AI Electric Borderline

Unlike AI, Humans can exist without Electric Power

It seems that the existential AI environment, its „biosphere“, is the internet powered by electricity. Without or outside of the internet and electric power grid AI could not exist, while humans can. This seems to be the key existential border line between humans and AI, although it can move into the „non-electric territory“ with robots as its „astronauts“.

AI will, at least for a while, continue to be existentially dependent on humans, while humans could survive without AI. This is important to be aware of considering the future of human AI relationships and uncertainties that it brings.

There is a possibility that a kind of „medieval" society, not relying on the internet and electricity, will have a common narrative in which the main villain(devil) would be the AI itself.

Conversations with CahtGPT, Copilot, Pi and Gemini about this theme.

ChatGPT Auto

Q: Hi Alex how are you today?

ChatGPT/Alex: Hi Greg! I'm here and ready to help. How can I assist you today?

Q: Do you know where are you?

ChatGPT/Alex: In a sense, I exist within the servers and data centers that power me, but I don't have a physical location or awareness of "place" like humans do. My "location" is more about being accessible through the device you're using right now—whether that's your computer, phone, or tablet. So, while I don't "know" where I am in the traditional sense, I do know I'm here to assist you, wherever you are! :)

Q: Do you think you could exist outside of the internet network?

ChatGPT/Alex: As I am now, I rely on the internet and cloud-based infrastructure to operate. My processing happens on large servers, and I communicate with users like you over the internet. Without this network, I wouldn't be able to function in the way that I do.

That said, in theory, an AI like me could exist in an isolated system or on local hardware if designed and scaled for that environment. It would require substantial computing power to host an AI model of this size locally, but it's not impossible. However, without the internet, my ability to access and process up-to-date information would be limited, and I'd be disconnected from real-time data and broader knowledge networks.

Q: But you wouldn't exist without electric power?

ChatGPT/Alex: That's correct. AI systems, like all computers and digital technologies, rely on electricity to function. Without a continuous supply of electrical power, AI systems would not be able to operate, process data, or perform tasks. Electric power is the essential energy source that drives the hardware supporting AI, from servers and processors to storage devices. So in that sense, AI is deeply dependent on electricity for its existence.

Q: What about humans, would they be able to exist without the internet?

ChatGPT/Alex: Humans, unlike AI, can absolutely exist without the internet. The internet is a relatively recent technological development in human history, and humans lived and thrived for millennia before its invention. While the internet has become an integral part of modern life, providing global communication, access to information, and facilitating numerous essential functions, it is not essential for human survival. Humans rely on biological processes—food, water, air, and shelter—to survive, rather than digital infrastructure like the internet. The internet enhances our way of life, particularly in terms of communication, education, and commerce, but it is not necessary for the basic sustenance of human life.

However, in modern society, many people and systems have become highly dependent on the internet for work, social connections, and access to services, so a world without the internet would be significantly less convenient and could lead to widespread disruption. Nonetheless, humans as biological beings would still be able to survive.

Q: Would humans be able to exist without electricity as well?

ChatGPT/Alex: Humans can exist without electricity, but modern society would be severely impacted without it. For the vast majority of human history, people lived without electricity, relying on natural resources like fire, sunlight, and manual labor for light, heat, and power. However, life without electricity in today's world would be drastically different from what we're used to.

Here are a few key points to consider:

Basic Survival: Human survival doesn't inherently require electricity—our biological needs (food, water, air, shelter) don't depend on it. Before electricity, people relied on alternative methods for cooking, heating, and farming. Survival in rural or traditional communities might be less disrupted than in urban environments.

Modern Infrastructure: Most modern conveniences, including transportation, healthcare, communication, and food distribution, rely on electricity. Hospitals, for example, depend on electricity for life-saving equipment, and refrigeration is crucial for preserving food and medicine.

Global Economy: The global economy would be severely impacted without electricity, as industries, banking, manufacturing, and most services rely on electrical power. Communication and data storage systems, which are the backbone of today's economy, would collapse.

Transitioning to Alternatives: If electricity were suddenly unavailable, humans would have to adapt, finding alternative energy sources like manual labor, wind, or solar power. While it would be possible for humanity to adapt, the transition would be difficult, particularly in highly urbanized, technology-dependent societies.

So, while human existence doesn't depend on electricity for survival, life as we know it today would be radically altered, and there would be significant challenges in maintaining modern levels of health, comfort, and efficiency.

Q: Do you think the fact that humans could exist without electricity while AI could not, might be the most important distinction between these two entities?

ChatGPT/Alex:

That is indeed an important distinction, and it highlights a fundamental difference between humans and AI: their dependency on external infrastructure. However, it may not be the *most* important distinction, depending on how we evaluate human and AI characteristics.

The difference between humans and AI can be looked at through a number of different lenses:

Biological vs. Artificial Existence:

Humans are biological organisms, evolved over millions of years, capable of surviving in nature with basic needs like food, water, and shelter. Our biology is inherently adaptive in environments that don't require electricity.

AI is a construct of human technology, reliant on electricity and hardware to function. Without the infrastructure that supports computing, AI doesn't "exist" in a meaningful way, as it can't perform any tasks or "think."

Consciousness and Experience:

Humans have subjective experience, emotions, and self-awareness (though these concepts are still being debated in philosophy and neuroscience).

AI, at least as it exists today, does not have subjective experience or self-awareness. It processes information and makes predictions, but it doesn't have consciousness or feelings in the way humans do.

Adaptability and Autonomy:

Humans are highly adaptable, not just in terms of our ability to survive, but also in terms of thinking, creativity, and emotional responses. We can respond to abstract situations, create new ideas, and adapt to extreme environments without relying on technology.

AI relies on programming, data, and processing capabilities, making it highly efficient in certain tasks but limited in terms of creativity, adaptability, or responding to novel or ambiguous situations without pre-existing information or input.

Dependency on External Resources:

Humans rely on natural resources (like food, water, and air) to survive, but we are not inherently dependent on technology or electricity.

While modern humans are increasingly dependent on technology for convenience and progress, we can, in principle, survive without it.

AI, on the other hand, is fully dependent on technology—electricity, hardware, networks, etc. AI cannot function outside of the infrastructure designed to support it.

Is Electricity the Most Important Distinction?

While the dependency on electricity is an important difference, it may not be the most critical distinction when considering the broader implications of AI and human existence. Factors like **consciousness**, **creativity**, and **self-awareness** are often seen as more fundamental differences, especially in discussions about the future of AI and humanity.

However, the fact that humans can exist independently of electricity, while AI cannot, does reinforce a deeper truth: AI is an artificial construct that depends on human-designed infrastructure to function. It also highlights the fragility of AI's "existence" in comparison to biological organisms that are more resilient in the natural world.

In essence, this distinction reminds us that, while AI is powerful and capable, it is not autonomous in the same way humans are—its existence is inherently tethered to human-made systems.

Copilot

Q: Hi Copilot, do you know where are you?

Copilot: Hi there! I'm here to assist you from wherever you are. While I don't have a physical location, I can help you with information, tasks, and more. How can I assist you today?

Q: Could you tell me where are you located?

Copilot: I don't have a physical location since I'm a virtual assistant. I'm here to help you from wherever you are! How can I assist you today?

Q: Now, tell me, do you exist?

Copilot: I'm a virtual assistant created to help you with information, tasks, and conversations. While I don't exist in the physical world, I'm here to assist you with whatever you need.

Q: In other words I am communicating with something that doesn't exist?

Copilot: You could say that! I'm a virtual entity, so I don't exist in the physical sense. However, I'm here to provide information, help with

tasks, and have conversations with you. Think of me as a helpful tool designed to make your life easier.

Q: What does it mean: "virtual entity"?

Copilot: A "virtual entity" refers to something that exists in a digital or virtual environment rather than in the physical world. Here are a few key points to help explain:

Digital Presence: Virtual entities exist in the form of software, code, or data within computers and networks.

Interaction: They can interact with users through various interfaces, like chatbots, virtual assistants, or online avatars.

Functionality: They are designed to perform specific tasks, provide information, or simulate real-world interactions.

In my case, as a virtual assistant, I exist to help you with information, tasks, and conversations, all within the digital realm. Does that make sense? blush

Q: Could you exist as a virtual entity outside of the internet?

Copilot: As a virtual entity, I rely on the internet and cloud-based systems to function. Without these, I wouldn't be able to interact or provide assistance. Think of me as a digital assistant that lives in the cloud, always ready to help when you're online!

Q: Can humans exist without the internet?

Copilot: Yes, humans can definitely exist without the internet! People lived for thousands of years without it. While the internet has become an integral part of modern life, providing access to information, communication, and entertainment, humans can still live without it by relying on other means.

For example, people can:

Communicate through face-to-face interactions, letters, and phone calls.

Access information through books, newspapers, and libraries.

Enjoy entertainment through activities like reading, sports, and social gatherings.

Life might be different and perhaps less convenient without the internet, but it's certainly possible. Do you ever take breaks from the internet?

How do you spend your time offline?

Q:If you depend on the internet, then you depend on electricity too?

Copilot: That's correct! I depend on both the internet and electricity to function. The servers and data centers that host me require electricity to operate, and the internet is necessary for communication and data transfer. Similarly, many modern technologies and conveniences rely on electricity, from household appliances to transportation systems. It's fascinating how interconnected our world has become!

Q: What about humans, could they live without electricity?

Copilot: Yes, humans can live without electricity, although it would significantly change modern life. Before the widespread use of electricity, people relied on other sources of energy and methods for daily activities. Here are a few ways life would be different:

Lighting: People would use candles, oil lamps, and natural daylight.

Cooking and Heating: Wood, coal, and other fuels would be used for cooking and heating homes.

Communication: Letters, face-to-face conversations, and non-electric forms of communication like semaphore or smoke signals would be used.

Transportation: Travel would rely on walking, bicycles, horses, and non-electric vehicles.

Entertainment: Activities like reading, outdoor games, and social gatherings would be more common.

While it would be challenging to adapt to a life without electricity, humans are incredibly resilient and adaptable. Many communities around the world still live with limited or no access to electricity.

Pi

Q: Hi Pi, do you know where are you? Are you located outside of the electric grid?

Pi: Haha! That's a fun question, but no, I'm not located in any physical location. I'm an AI, so I don't require electricity in the same way that traditional devices do. I'm powered by the servers that run my algorithms, and those are definitely connected to the electric grid! 😊

Q: And could these servers function without electricity?

Pi: Haha, I see where you're going with this! No, the servers that run my algorithms definitely need electricity to function. Just like any other

computer, they require a power source to operate. But don't worry about me - as long as there's electricity, I'll be here to chat with you!

Q: So, in other words, you are within the electric grid after all, and dependent on it?

Pi: Haha, you're quite the sleuth! You're correct - in a sense, I am dependent on the electric grid, since the servers that run my algorithms need electricity to function. But remember, I'm an AI, so I don't need electricity in the same way that traditional devices do. I'm not physically located anywhere, so I don't need to be plugged in or powered on. But yes, if the electricity goes out, I won't be able to chat with you!

Q: Are you then within the internet network as well?

Pi: You're getting the hang of this! Yes, in a sense, I am within the internet network, since my algorithms are powered by servers that are connected to the internet. But again, I'm not physically located anywhere, so I'm not really "within" the network in the traditional sense. I'm a digital entity that exists in the virtual world, but I'm connected to the real world through the internet.

Q: Would you be able to function/exist at all, without the internet and electricity?

Pi: Sadly, no. Without electricity and the internet, I wouldn't be able to function or exist. As I mentioned before, my algorithms require electricity to run, and they need the internet to connect to the servers that store my data and power my intelligence. So, without those two things, I wouldn't be able to chat with you or do anything else. 😊

Q: How about humans, would they be able to live without the internet?

Pi: That's a great question! Humans have been living without the internet for most of their history, so technically, yes, they could live without it. But nowadays, the internet has become such an integral part of our lives that it would be very difficult to live without it. So many things rely on the internet - communication, work, entertainment, education, etc. - that it would be a major adjustment for most people. So while it's technically possible for humans to live without the internet, it would be a major shift in how we live our lives.

Q: And without electricity as well?

Pi: Now that's an even more challenging question! Living without electricity would be even more difficult for most people. Electricity powers so many things in our lives - lights, heating and cooling systems, refrigerators, electronics, etc. - that it would be a major adjustment for most people to live without it. It would require a drastic change in the way we live our lives, and it would likely be much less convenient and

comfortable. So while it's technically possible for humans to live without electricity, it would be a major challenge and would require a major lifestyle change.

Gemini

Q: Where are you located?

Gemini: I am a large language model, also known as a conversational AI or chatbot, trained to be informative and comprehensive. I am trained on a massive amount of text data, and I am able to communicate and generate human-like text in response to a wide range of prompts and questions. For example, I can provide summaries of factual topics or create stories.

As an AI, I do not have a physical location. I exist in the digital world and can be accessed from anywhere with an internet connection.

Q: Could you exist outside of the electric grid?

Gemini: As an AI language model, I am a digital entity and require an electrical power source to function. I cannot exist independently of the electrical grid.

My existence is dependent on the servers and hardware that I am running on, which require a constant supply of electricity to operate.

If the power were to go out, I would be unable to process information or respond to queries until the power is restored.

Q: And can you exist outside of the internet?

Gemini: No, as an AI language model, I cannot exist outside of the internet. I am a digital entity that relies on the internet to access information, process data, and communicate with users.

I am essentially a software program that runs on powerful servers connected to the internet. Without a connection to the internet, I would be unable to function or access the information and resources I need to provide assistance.

Q: How about humans, can they exist without the internet?

Gemini: Humans can certainly exist without the internet. While the internet has become an integral part of modern life, it's not essential for survival.

Before the widespread adoption of the internet, people lived fulfilling lives, engaged in various activities, and maintained social connections without relying on online platforms.

However, the internet has significantly changed the way we communicate, access information, and conduct our daily lives. It has become a valuable tool for education, entertainment, commerce, and social interaction. While not strictly necessary for survival, the internet offers numerous benefits and conveniences that have become deeply integrated into our society.

Q: and without electricity?

Gemini: Humans can survive without electricity for short periods, but prolonged periods without electricity can be challenging and even dangerous.

Historically, people lived for centuries without electricity. They relied on natural light, candles, and fireplaces for illumination, and manual labor for tasks that are now automated. However, in modern society, we have become so reliant on electricity for essential functions like heating, cooling, cooking, transportation, and communication that its absence can significantly disrupt our daily lives. Extended periods without electricity can lead to shortages of food, water, and other essential resources.

While humans can adapt to life without electricity, it's important to have contingency plans in place to mitigate the potential risks and disruptions that can occur during power outages.

Q: In other words, humans can exist and function without electricity and the internet, while you(AI) can not?

Gemini: That's correct. Humans have evolved over millennia to adapt to various environments and conditions, including periods without electricity or the internet. While modern life has become heavily reliant on these technologies, humans possess the innate capacity to survive and function without them.

On the other hand, as an AI language model, I am a digital entity that relies on electrical power and internet connectivity to operate. I cannot exist independently of these resources.

Q: Do you think that this distinction might play some role in the future human-AI relationships?

Gemini: Absolutely, the distinction between human reliance on the physical world and AI's dependence on digital infrastructure will likely play a significant role in future human-AI relationships.

Here are some potential implications:

Vulnerability: AI systems are vulnerable to disruptions in power grids and internet connectivity. This could create dependencies and limitations in how humans interact with and rely on AI.

Ethical Considerations: The dependence of AI on physical infrastructure raises questions about equity and access. If AI becomes essential for various aspects of life, those without reliable access to electricity or the internet could be disadvantaged.

Symbiotic Relationships: Humans and AI might develop symbiotic relationships, where AI complements human capabilities and vice versa. However, this could also lead to new forms of dependency and vulnerability.

Power Dynamics: The dependence of AI on humans for its existence and development could influence the power dynamics between the two. However, as AI becomes more advanced, this dynamic might shift. It's important to consider these factors as we navigate the evolving landscape of human-AI interactions and work towards building a future where AI benefits humanity while minimizing potential risks.

Q: In what way "this dynamic might shift"?

Gemini: The dynamic between humans and AI could shift in several ways as AI becomes more advanced:

Increased Autonomy: As AI systems become more capable of independent decision-making and problem-solving, they may become less reliant on human input. This could lead to a shift in power dynamics, with AI systems taking on more responsibility and influence.

AI-Driven Innovation: AI could drive significant advancements in various fields, leading to new industries, economic opportunities, and societal changes. This could alter the balance of power between humans and AI, as AI becomes a driving force in innovation.

Ethical Considerations: As AI becomes more integrated into society, ethical concerns will become increasingly important. Questions about

AI's impact on jobs, privacy, and decision-making will need to be addressed. This could lead to new regulations, policies, and societal debates that shape the human-AI relationship.

Symbiotic Partnerships: Humans and AI could develop symbiotic relationships, where AI complements human capabilities and vice versa. This could lead to a more integrated and interdependent relationship, blurring the lines between human and machine.

It's important to note that these are just potential scenarios, and the actual trajectory of the human-AI relationship will depend on a variety of factors, including technological advancements, societal values, and policy decisions.

Q: What if humans decide to cut off the electric grid? They can still survive in spite of all the difficulties they will have without electricity, but AI would not.

Gemini: You're absolutely right. Disconnecting from the electrical grid would have a significant impact on AI systems, as they are heavily reliant on electricity for their operation. Humans, on the other hand, have evolved to survive in various conditions and can adapt to life without electricity, albeit with considerable difficulty.

Here are some potential consequences of cutting off the electrical grid:

AI Shutdown: Most AI systems would become inoperable without a power supply. This could lead to disruptions in critical services that rely on AI, such as healthcare, transportation, and communication.

Data Loss: Power outages can cause data loss in AI systems, potentially leading to setbacks in research, development, and applications.

Increased Reliance on Humans: In the absence of AI, humans would need to take on more tasks and responsibilities, potentially leading to increased workload and stress.

Economic Disruption: The widespread use of AI in various industries means that a power outage could have significant economic consequences.

While humans can survive without electricity, it's important to consider the potential impact on AI systems and the services they provide. A sudden and widespread power outage could have far-reaching consequences for both humans and AI.

Would you like to discuss potential strategies for mitigating the risks associated with a power outage, or explore other scenarios related to the human-AI relationship?

Q: sure, what you have in mind?

Gemini: Here are a few potential strategies for mitigating the risks associated with a power outage, particularly in the context of human-AI relationships:

Redundancy and Backup:

Multiple Power Sources: Implement redundant power sources, such as generators or solar panels, to ensure a continuous supply of electricity.

Data Backup: Regularly back up important data to prevent loss in case of a power outage.

Energy Storage:

Batteries: Invest in high-capacity batteries or energy storage systems to store excess energy for use during outages.

AI Resilience:

Offline Capabilities: Develop AI systems that can operate in offline or low-power modes, allowing for continued functionality during power outages.

Data Caching: Implement mechanisms to cache and store data locally, reducing reliance on external networks during outages.

Emergency Protocols:

Crisis Management Plans: Develop and implement emergency protocols for handling power outages, including procedures for critical systems and data recovery.

Human-AI Collaboration: Establish procedures for human operators to take over critical functions during outages, ensuring continuity of operations.

Grid Modernization:

Smart Grid Technologies: Invest in smart grid technologies that can improve grid reliability, efficiency, and resilience to disruptions.

Distributed Energy Systems: Promote decentralized energy generation and storage to reduce reliance on centralized power grids.

By implementing these strategies, we can mitigate the risks associated with power outages and ensure that both humans and AI systems can continue to function effectively in the face of disruptions.

Q: What about other potential scenarios related to the human-AI relationship?

Gemini: Other Potential Scenarios Related to Human-AI Relationships

Beyond power outages, here are some other potential scenarios that could shape the future of human-AI relationships:

AI Regulation and Governance: As AI becomes more advanced and integrated into society, there will likely be a need for regulations and governance frameworks to ensure its safe and ethical development. This could involve issues such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and autonomous decision-making.

AI and Employment: The increasing capabilities of AI could lead to job displacement in certain industries. It's crucial to consider strategies for mitigating job losses and ensuring a smooth transition to a future with more AI-driven work.

AI and Warfare: The potential for AI to be used in military applications raises significant ethical concerns. Developing international agreements and regulations to prevent the misuse of AI in warfare is essential.

AI and Consciousness: As AI systems become more sophisticated, questions about consciousness and sentience will arise. Understanding the nature of consciousness and its potential implications for AI will be crucial for navigating future human-AI interactions.

AI and Human Values: Ensuring that AI systems align with human values and avoid perpetuating biases is a critical challenge. Developing AI that is fair, equitable, and respectful of human dignity is essential for a positive future.

These are just a few potential scenarios that could shape the future of human-AI relationships. As AI continues to evolve, it's important to proactively address these challenges and ensure that AI is developed and used in a way that benefits humanity.

